

**Deliverable D1.3:
Report on Annual Meeting 2025**

Project information

Project full title	Research Infrastructure Access in NANoscience & nanotechnology
Project acronym	RIANA
Grant agreement no.	101130652
Instrument	Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Duration	01.03.2024 – 29.02.2028
Website	riana-project.eu

Deliverable information

Deliverable no.	1.3
Deliverable title	Annual Meeting Report 1
Deliverable responsible	DESY
Related Work-Package/Task	WP1
Type (e.g. Report; other)	R – Document, Report
Author(s)	Tom Minniberger, Michael Stuckelberger
Author(s) affiliation	DESY
Dissemination level	PU – Public
Document Version	1
Date	01.05.2025
Download page	https://riana-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/D1.3_RIANA_Annual_Meeting_2025.pdf

Document information

Version no.	Date	Author(s)	Comment
0.1	14.04.2025	Tom Minniberger	Draft document
0.2	29.04.2025	Michael Stuckelberger	Finalization

Reference

DOI	10.5281/zenodo.20001735
URL	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20001735

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	2
1. Introduction	3
2. Day 1	5
3. Day 2	7
4. Programme of the 1 st RIANA Annual Meeting 2025	8

Executive Summary

This deliverable gives an overview of the 1st RIANA Annual Meeting that took place 19 – 20 February 2025 in Padriciano/Trieste, Italy, and was hosted by the leader of work package 2. The highly successful meeting combined strategic discussions, technical exchanges, and networking activities, thereby supporting the effective implementation of the Horizon Europe project.

Scheduling the RIANA Annual Meeting back-to-back with the Annual Meeting of the EU project LEAPS-INNOV ensured diligent use of resources and fostered inter-project collaboration. Within the two days of the RIANA Annual Meeting, RIANA bodies including the General Assembly, Executive Board, Junior Scientist Board, and Nano Strategy Board profited from satellite meetings that were held in hybrid mode as the entire RIANA Annual Meeting.

Overall, the 1st RIANA Annual Meeting 2025 met its objectives. It provided a comprehensive review of the first project year and allowed to align on the work plan and its interdependencies, strengthened collaboration and team spirit across the consortium, and set the course for intensified promotion and use of RIANA's services in the years ahead.

1. Introduction

Key figures

The 1st RIANA Annual Meeting was held as a hybrid meeting on 19 – 20 February 2025 at AREA Science Park in Padriciano/Trieste, Italy. The Annual Meeting 2025 gathered 105 participants from 19 countries: Italy, Germany, the Netherlands, Poland, Norway, France, Romania, Estonia, Spain, the Czech Republic, Lithuania, Croatia, Austria, the United Kingdom, Belgium, Portugal, Greece, Sweden, and Slovenia. The majority of 80 participants joined in person (see Fig. 1) and 25 connected remotely via Zoom. Almost all project partners were represented at the Annual Meeting. The consortium reviewed the implementation of the first project year and the work planned for the years to come.

Outreach video

During the two meeting days, a video was produced by the local organizer AREA Science Park with the title “RIANA, your gateway to nanoscience and nanotechnology” to advertise the RIANA Transnational Access possibilities and to represent the important role of AREA Science Park in the RIANA consortium (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EbEKTJuDweY>).

Figure 1: RIANA group photo of the Annual Meeting 2025. Credit: Giulia Coppetti.

Strengthening connection to LEAPS-INNOV EU-Project

The RIANA Annual Meeting 2025 was organized back-to-back to the Annual Meeting of the LEAPS-INNOV EU-Project (project number: 101004728). As numerous project partners are represented in both projects, it was possible for some participants to attend both meetings, thereby saving on travel costs and fostering inter-project collaboration.

The RIANA Annual Meeting 2025 brought together the project partners of the large consortium to review the processes and achievements of the first project year, to motivate all beneficiaries to intensify their efforts to promote RIANA's services, to strengthen cooperation within the consortium, and to present the strategy for the coming project years.

Informal networking dinner

The event began with an informal networking dinner on the evening before the official opening of the meeting, at the participants' own expense. In a relaxed atmosphere, partners discussed project-related matters as well as personal topics, which helped to build trust and strengthen interpersonal connections within the consortium (see Fig. 2). This get-together provided an excellent starting point for the annual meeting and offered valuable opportunities for informal exchange and networking.

Figure 2: Informal networking dinner. Credit: Catalin-Daniel Constantinescu.

2. Day 1

Executive Board meeting & site visit

The first official morning was dedicated to a meeting of the RIANA Executive Board (EB) and a visit to the AREA/CNR/Elettra facilities. During the site visit, the project partners received an excellent overview of the measurement possibilities and research infrastructures available on site, which are highly relevant for RIANA's service portfolio. This helped align the scientific and technical capacities of the hosting institutions with the needs of current and future RIANA users.

Figure 3: Visit of AREA/CNR/Elettra facilities. Credit: Catalin-Daniel Constantinescu.

Plenary presentations

In the afternoon, the participants were officially welcomed by Caterina Petrillo, President of Area Science Park, and Regina Ciancio, Head of the Electron Microscopy Laboratory at Area Science Park. Both underlined the importance of RIANA for their institution and for the wider nanoscience and nanotechnology community. The European Commission's RIANA project manager Anna Santoro then presented, among other points, a preliminary outlook on the next framework programme, FP10, thus placing RIANA within the broader EU research policy context. The first session concluded with a presentation by project coordinator Michael Stuckelberger (DESY), who provided an overview of the status of RIANA applications. Inspired by an illustration from Antoine de Saint-Exupéry's "Le Petit Prince", he highlighted the shared ambition to significantly increase the number of RIANA users in the coming years of the project.

Parallel work package discussions

Following a group photo presented in Fig. 1, the consortium split into parallel working group meetings dedicated to the individual work packages (WPs). The aim of these meetings was to review progress, address current action points, and identify upcoming tasks within each WP.

Plenary discussions & Junior Scientist Board meeting

In the second part of the afternoon, all partners reconvened in the auditorium for a joint discussion across all work packages (see Fig. 4), focusing on interfaces, synergies, and challenges to be addressed at the consortium level. In parallel to the first part of these plenary discussions, the Junior Scientists Board (JSB) held its own meeting. After the conclusion of the JSB meeting, the RIANA junior scientists (see Fig. 5) joined the plenary session in the auditorium and were officially introduced to the consortium on stage, as their recruitment had been completed during the first year of the project. To

symbolically welcome them to the RIANA community, the junior scientists received the traditional RIANA gift, a cactus.

Figure 4: Plenary session of the RIANA Annual Meeting 2025. Credit: Catalin-Daniel Constantinescu.

Working dinner

In the evening, a working dinner provided an additional opportunity to continue discussions within and between the work packages, and to explore further constructive ideas and solutions to implement the project's visions on scientific, technical, and management levels. The coordinator delivered a speech that emphasized the importance of collaboration, mutual support, and shared objectives, thereby reinforcing the sense of team spirit and common vision among the project partners.

3. Day 2

General Assembly

The second day of the annual meeting started with the General Assembly (GA) meeting to which all participants of the Annual Meeting were invited. Four decisions were put to the GA members with voting rights:

- (1) the launch of the first amendment to the RIANA Grant Agreement
- (2) the appointment of three new members to the RIANA Nano Strategy Board
- (3) the introduction of additional access rules to limit excessive access requests
- (4) the approval of a procedure to allocate 5 new Junior Scientist positions and to allocate Transnational Access from the reserve funding

All four decisions were adopted unanimously by the RIANA General Assembly.

Plenary presentations

The second day of the annual meeting focused on consolidation, reporting, and forward planning. The work package leaders and co-leaders presented the six work packages and reported to the full consortium on the outcomes of their WP meetings from Day 1. They outlined key activities, main achievements of the first project year, and next steps, while also highlighting interdependencies and connections with other WPs to ensure coherent implementation of the overall work plan. In addition, Tom Minniberger from the DESY EU Office presented the main requirements, rules, and obligations for Horizon Europe projects and requested all beneficiaries to contribute to the interim financial report by submitting their project-related expenses incurred during the first 12-month project period.

Figure 5: Junior Scientists at the RIANA Annual Meeting 2025. Credit: Catalin-Daniel Constantinescu.

4. Programme of the 1st RIANA Annual Meeting 2025

Tuesday, February 18, 2025

Time	Activity	Place
19:30	Informal dinner (at own expense)	Trieste city center

Wednesday, February 19, 2025

Time	Activity	Place
09:00 – 10:00	RIANA Executive Board (EB) Meeting - <i>Closed session</i> (EB members, coordinator)	Area Science Park, Basovizza Campus
09:00 – 11:30	Visit to AREA/CNR/Elettra facilities	Area Science Park, Basovizza Campus
12:00	Registration	
12:30	Lunch	
13:30	Welcome Regina Ciancio , Head of the Electron Microscopy Laboratory Caterina Petrillo , President of Area Science Park	Area Congress Center
13:45	Introductory statement Anna Santoro , Policy Officer, European Research Executive Agency (REA)	Area Congress Center
13:55	Coordinator welcome Michael Stuckelberger , Project Coordinator (DESY)	Area Congress Center
14:10	GROUP PICTURE	
14:30	Parallel session 1 (WP meetings) WP 2: Meeting Room WP 3: Conference Hall WP 4: Sala Conferenze WP 5: Auditorium WP 6: EEN room	Area Congress Center
16:00	Coffee break	

16:30	Parallel session 2 (Interlinks between WPs) All WPs together: Conference hall JSB: Oval room DEI Officers: PRP Chairs:	
17:30	Plenary (Q&A session with EB)	Area Congress Center
18:30	End of 1st day meeting	
20:00	Working dinner	Trieste city center

Thursday, February 20, 2025

Time	Activity	Place
09:00	GA Meeting (Conference hall) <i>Open to all project partners</i>	Area Congress Center (Padriciano)
10:00	User access User access: status today Michael Stuckelberger, Project Coordinator (DESY) Process flow Marketa Sjögren, WP3 Manager (MAXIV) User access for SME & industry Giancarlo Panaccione, WP Leader (CNR)	Area Congress Center
10:30	WP presentations WP 1: Management Michael Stuckelberger, Project Coordinator (DESY) Tom Minniberger, Project Manager (DESY) WP 2: Customised access to scientific service Regina Ciancio, WP Leader (AREA) Rafal Dunin-Borkowski, WP co-Leader (FZJ) WP 3: Customised access to research infrastructure Marketa Sjögren, WP Manager (MAXIV) Daniela Stozno, WP co-Leader (Laserlab AISBL) WP 4: Customised access to innovation service Giancarlo Panaccione, WP Leader (CNR)	Area Congress Center
11:00	Coffee break	

11:30	WP presentations WP 5: Training and education Panagiotis Loukakos, WP Leader (FORTH) WP 6: Outreach, dissemination, and impact Gaston Garcia, WP Leader (UAM)	
11:45	RIANA committees Junior Scientist Board Chair of JSB and all JS PRP Chairs Chairs of PRP DEI Officers Inka Manek-Hönniger & Lakshmi Bhaskaran	Area Congress Center
12:20	Outlook	
12:30	Q&A, AOB, farewell	
13:00	Lunch (14.00: End of meeting)	